

NPDS FAIR Search Engines with Interoperable Exchange of the Free Flow of Findable Facts in Open Collaboration Networks

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1. Abstract:

Early adopters of the World Wide Web found information through human-curated web portals and directories (Zhou, 2003). However, as the number of websites exploded, only search engines using automated crawlers could keep pace, and the companies with the biggest databases and fastest results became default gateways to the Web (Escandell-Poveda et al., 2022). This centralization and the resulting competition for top rankings in search results created information choke points (Van Couvering, 2008), profit motives for biasing search results (Rieder & Sire, 2014), and circulation of claims without attribution to their original sources (Gangopadhyay et al., 2024). Even in an age of abundant information, obfuscation of its origin and quality leads to “information malnutrition” (Herman & Nicholas, 2010). Large language models (LLMs) have exacerbated these concerns, as they obfuscate the sources of their training data and can even respond to attempts to enforce guardrails and transparency by disguising their generative processes (Baker et al., 2025).

Since 2006, the PORTAL-DOORS Project (PDP) has been developing software infrastructure for a democratized and transparent approach to search (Taswell et al., 2006). The original motivating problem was integration of evidence from multiple types of studies into meta-analyses of hypotheses about neurodegenerative disorders (Taswell, 2007; Skarzynski et al., 2015), but the PDP software can support knowledge engineering in any problem domain (Dutta et al., 2020). Use cases include clinical telegaming (Taswell, 2010b), curation of cultural artifacts (Athreya et al., 2021), and analysis of scholarly literature itself, specifically use of the Fair Attribution of Indexed Reports (FAIR) Metrics to study how both authors (Craig et al., 2023) and reviewers (Craig & Taswell, 2024) make clear or obfuscate the origins of their factual claims.

The defining features of PDP software are the messaging protocol and REST API of the Nexus-PORTAL-DOORS-Scribe (NPDS) cyberinfrastructure (Craig et al., 2016), which enable distribution of data and metadata records across multiple repositories (Taswell, 2010a), even alternate implementations built on different software solution stacks (Craig et al., 2017). By implementing these specifications in free, open source, full-stack server software (github.com/BHAVIUS/PDP-DREAM), Brain Health Alliance (BHA) empowers individuals and organizations to host their own data and metadata in searchable repositories (Anand & Taswell, 2022). Interoperability between repositories enables organizations to share records easily in support of the free flow of findable facts (Athreya et al., 2023), as demonstrated by repositories that BHA hosts at portaldoors.net, brainhealthalliance.net, and brainwatch.net.

By including semantic knowledge graphs that describe the key claims of works, NPDS records can fill a gap in the metadata available from major scholarly publishers (Craig et al., 2020) and support unambiguous identification of equal or equivalent entities through URIs (Athreya et al., 2020). Such semantic descriptions could support question-answering systems based on semantic query engines (Antoniou & Bassiliades, 2022). Even when expanding queries over billions of semantic triples, these

rarely need billions of operations (Abdelaziz et al., 2017; Samsi et al., 2023), allowing independent organizations to use their own locally hosted AI instead of monolithic LLMs belonging to large corporations, further democratizing information discovery.

2. References

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